

Parameter Uncertainty Estimation in NMR Spectral Fitting Using ssNake

Estimating the uncertainty of fit parameters using the χ^2 method

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Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy is a non-destructive method of elucidating molecular structures. NMR spectra are obtained and subsequently fitted to extract quantitative parameters. Although noise in the spectrum introduces uncertainty in the fitted parameters, the associated errors are rarely reported in NMR studies. This work aims to improve accessibility to parameter uncertainty estimation in NMR spectral fitting by presenting a practical method and integrating it into the NMR analysis software ssNake. Uncertainties of the fit parameters were estimated from the curvature of the chi-squared (χ^2) surface by inverting the matrix of second order derivatives to obtain the covariance matrix. The square roots of the diagonal elements were taken as the parameter uncertainties and scaled to reflect joint confidence intervals. The χ^2 -based uncertainty estimation method was successfully integrated into ssNake and shown to be viable for spectral fitting. The current method has shortcomings: it slightly underestimates uncertainties likely due to a subtle mischaracterization of the theoretical model and nonlinear parameter correlations introduce non-quadratic behavior near the chi-squared minimum, reducing the reliability of the estimates. While the current approach provides a promising foundation, several features—such as multi-peak fitting, proper parameter rounding, and goodness-of-fit testing—must still be implemented before it is suited for practical use in NMR analysis.

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Introduction

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, or NMR spectroscopy for short, is a technique used to elucidate molecular structures. It is a nondestructive method that takes advantage of the magnetic properties of certain nuclei to detect their chemical environment. NMR spectroscopy is widely used in applied research in chemistry, biology, medicine, and materials science.

NMR spectra are commonly fitted to extract quantitative values for specific parameters. However, the presence of noise in the spectra affects the precision with which these parameters can be determined. In many other fields, it is common practice to estimate uncertainties by analyzing multiple independent measurements.

In NMR spectroscopy, spectra are typically constructed by averaging the signal from multiple independent scans to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. However, calculating parameter uncertainties based on these individual measurements would not accurately reflect the uncertainties of the final, averaged spectrum, which has reduced noise and thus smaller uncertainties. Consequently, acquiring multiple independent, low-noise spectra for the purpose of estimating uncertainties is uncommon, as it is time consuming and often impractical. In practice, additional measurements are rarely performed unless necessary for resolving specific features, as standard acquisition typically aims for acceptable signal-to-noise rather than uncertainty analysis.

Alternative methods of calculating the uncertainty are often less straightforward and more time consuming. Despite the widespread use of NMR spectroscopy, there is a lack of standardized methods or guidelines for estimating uncertainties in fitted parameters. Moreover, most NMR processing software does not include functionality for estimating uncertainties in fitted parameters.

For example, a thorough review of the documentation for the widely used Bruker TopSpin software revealed no built-in tools for estimating parameter uncertainties from spectral fits [1] [2]. General-purpose scientific libraries such as SciPy (Python) and MATLAB [3] [4] do provide some functionality for error estimation, but these are typically based on assumptions of homoscedastic noise (i.e., uniform variance), which generally hold in NMR spectra, but may be violated under non-ideal conditions [5]. Furthermore, these tools are not tailored for NMR-specific workflows and often require substantial custom implementation. More fundamentally, the precision and accuracy of fitted parameters also depend heavily on how well the spectral model captures the actual peak shapes, overlaps, and baseline characteristics, making model selection a critical factor in uncertainty

estimation.

As a result of these limitations, the estimation of uncertainties in fitted parameters remains a significant challenge in NMR spectroscopy. This challenge is reflected in the widespread absence of rigorous uncertainty reporting in the NMR literature.

Uncertainty analysis is an essential aspect of scientific research. It acknowledges the inherent limitations of any measurement or experiment. Since observations are rarely perfectly precise, quantifying uncertainty allows scientists to express the confidence level of their results. Error reporting allows others to accurately interpret findings, compare results across studies, and assess the reliability of conclusions. By clearly reporting uncertainties, researchers make their work more reproducible and easier to validate. It also supports informed decision making by clarifying the reliability and limitations of the results. Additionally, doing an uncertainty analysis provides insight into the limitations of the experiment and helps identify areas that have room for improvement. Ultimately, uncertainty analysis and error reporting enhance the reliability and reproducibility of scientific research.

This work aims to improve accessibility to parameter uncertainty estimation in NMR spectral fitting by presenting a practical method and integrating it into the NMR analysis software ssNake. The method is based on a χ^2 (chi squared) analysis of the fit, which estimates the uncertainty of each parameter by evaluating how the fit quality changes as parameters are varied. It is closely related to least-squares fitting, an approach already used in ssNake. This method provides a statistically grounded means of quantifying (joint) confidence intervals for fitted values. It can be used for heteroscedastic noise and works separately from the fitting protocol, as opposed to the tools provided by SciPy and MATLAB. This allows for the method to be tailored for NMR spectral fitting. By implementing this method within ssNake, this work addresses the current lack of accessible tools for uncertainty estimation in NMR spectroscopy.

Chapter 2

Theory

The following section introduces the theoretical foundations necessary for understanding the uncertainty estimation outlined in this paper, focusing on relevant aspects of NMR spectroscopy and statistical analysis.

2.1 NMR spectroscopy

This section provides a simplified overview of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, based primarily on the textbook *Applied NMR Spectroscopy for Chemists and Life Scientists* by Zerbe et al. [6]. The goal is to provide general context for the thesis; a detailed understanding of NMR theory is not required for the remainder of this work.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy is a technique that makes use of the magnetic properties of certain atomic nuclei to determine the structure of molecules. Certain nuclei possess nuclear spin, which gives rise to a small magnetic dipole moment. The relationship between a nucleus' intrinsic magnetic moment and its spin is defined by the gyromagnetic ratio (γ), which is a specific constant unique to each type of nucleus.

When nuclei with a non-zero spin are placed in an external magnetic field, their magnetic moment tends to align either with or against the field. This gives rise to two different energy levels in the case of spin-1/2 nuclei: the lower energy state for a parallel alignment and the higher energy state for an antiparallel alignment. NMR spectroscopy induces and observes transitions between these energy states by using radiofrequency pulses to excite the nuclei. The magnetic moment undergoes a rotational motion around the direction of the magnetic field, much like a spinning top. This rotational motion is known as precession, and its frequency, called the Larmor frequency (ω_0), is what is measured in NMR spectroscopy.

$$\omega_0 = -\gamma B_0 \tag{2.1}$$

Because the Larmor frequency depends on the gyromagnetic ratio (γ), which is unique to each type of nucleus, it allows identification of the nucleus being observed. Structural information, however, arises from small variations in the resonance frequency due to interactions such as chemical shift, J-coupling, dipolar coupling, and quadrupolar interactions (for nuclei with spin $I > \frac{1}{2}$), which are

sensitive to the chemical environment. To detect an NMR signal, the spin system must first be disturbed using a brief burst of radiofrequency (RF) energy, known as an RF pulse. The resulting precession of the disturbed magnetization generates a changing magnetic field that induces an alternating electrical signal in a nearby detection coil. This signal is known as the free induction decay (FID). The FID contains a range of frequencies corresponding to the Larmor precession frequencies of spins in different chemical environments.

To interpret the FID, a Fourier Transform is applied, converting the time-domain signal into a frequency-domain spectrum. This NMR spectrum shows peaks at specific resonance frequencies corresponding to different chemical environments of the nuclei in the molecule. The spectrum is often fit to extract quantitative information. Individual peaks are typically modeled using Lorentzian or Gaussian line shapes or a combination of both to accurately describe their appearance. By fitting peaks using the Lorentzian/Gaussian fit function, key parameters such as position, integral and Lorentzian and Gaussian character can be determined.

The processing and fitting of NMR data is done with the help of NMR software. One such software is ssNake, an open source NMR data processing and analysis program, with a focus on solid state NMR [7] [8]. It is developed by Radboud University's Magnetic Resonance Research Center (MRRC) [9].

The methods of estimating the uncertainties of the fit parameters described in this paper, apply to 1D high-resolution solid-state NMR spectra. The focus lies on the Lorentzian/Gaussian fit function. The implementation of the code is integrated in ssNake.

2.2 Statistics

2.2.1 Random and systematic errors

Generally, a distinction is made between two types of errors: random errors and systematic errors [10]. Random errors affect the precision of a measurement, whereas systematic errors affect the accuracy. See Figure 2.1. In this paper, the focus will lie on random errors.

Figure 2.1 Random and systematic errors in target practice. (a) Because all shots arrived close to one another, we can tell the random errors are small. Because the distribution of shots is centered on the center of the target, the systematic errors are also small. (b) The random errors are still small, but the systematic ones are much larger—the shots are "systematically" off-center toward the right. (c) Here, the random errors are large, but the systematic ones are small—the shots are widely scattered but not systematically off-center. (d) Here, both random and systematic errors are large. Figure from Introduction to error analysis, the study of uncertainties in physical measurements by John R. Taylor [11].

2.2.2 Variance, covariance and the standard deviation

Figure 2.2 Two histograms with the same median, same average, and same most probable value, but different standard deviations.

Figure from Introduction to Quantum Mechanics by David J. Griffiths [12].

Figure 2.2 shows two histograms with the same median, same average and same most probable value, but that still look very different. The right figure is much more spread out than the left one. A measure of how much the data is spread out from its mean is called their variance [13].

$$\text{Var}(x) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \mu)^2}{n} \quad (2.2)$$

Here, μ represents the true (but generally unknown) mean of the underlying distribution, and n is the number of data points. In practical applications, this true mean is rarely accessible, so it is typically approximated by the arithmetic mean of the available data. In statistics, this situation is handled using sample estimators, which are designed to infer properties of the underlying distribution from a finite set of observations. Say, for instance, when doing research on the average height of people in the Netherlands, the true mean μ would denote the mean taken over every single person in the Netherlands. Measuring the height of every single person in the Netherlands would be unfeasible. Therefore, a sample population would be used to estimate this average instead. The interpretation of this in experimental research would be that a property has some unknown, true value and every measurement of it is an approximation of this value. For example, the sample variance is used to estimate the true variance, and is defined as follows [14]:

$$\text{Var}(x) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1} \quad (2.3)$$

Where \bar{x} is the average value of x , n is the number of data points¹. In this paper, terms such as variance, standard deviation, and mean refer to these sample-based statistical estimators unless

¹The reason that Equation 2.3 divides by $n - 1$ instead of n is that it represents the *sample variance*, not the *population variance*. The key point is that the mean \bar{x} is calculated from the same data set used to compute the variance, which introduces a bias toward underestimating the true variance. To compensate for this bias, *Bessel's correction* is applied by dividing by $n - 1$ instead of n [14].

explicitly stated otherwise. It is important to note that, although the language of “sampling” is used, the data analyzed in this work typically come from a single experimental dataset. The sample estimators are used not in the context of repeated measurements or sampling a population, but as standard statistical tools for analyzing the uncertainty and variability within that single dataset.

The standard deviation is the square root of the variance:

$$\sigma(x) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1}} \quad (2.4)$$

The uncertainty of the standard deviation²:

$$\delta s = \frac{s}{\sqrt{2n - 2}} \quad (2.5)$$

Where s is the standard deviation and n is the number of samples used.

Covariance is a statistical measure that describes how two variables change together.

$$\text{Cov}(x,y) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{n - 1} \quad (2.6)$$

A positive covariance indicates that the variables tend to increase or decrease together, while a negative covariance suggests that as one increases, the other tends to decrease. If the covariance is close to zero, the variables are likely uncorrelated in a linear sense [15]. See Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3 The sign of the covariance of two random variables X and Y. Image from Wikipedia [16]

When a variable is compared with itself, its covariance reduces to its variance.

$$\text{Cov}(x,x) = \text{Var}(x) \quad (2.7)$$

2.2.3 The normal distribution

A normal distribution is a symmetric, bell-shaped curve that represents how data are distributed around a central mean, with the highest frequency of values near the mean and progressively fewer observations as you move further away. When a measurement is affected by many small,

²See Appendix B.

independent random errors, its distribution tends to approximate a normal distribution [11]. The probability density function is:

$$f_{\sigma,\mu}(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2} \quad (2.8)$$

Where σ is the standard deviation and μ is the (true) mean. For the normal distribution, 68.3 percent of the values lie within one standard deviation from the mean. Two standard deviations from the mean account for 95.5 percent and three standard deviations for 99.7 percent. See Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4 The normal distribution. Here, σ is the standard deviation and μ is the (true) mean. For the normal distribution, 68.27 percent of the values lie within one standard deviation from the mean. Two standard deviations from the mean account for 95.45 percent and three standard deviations for 99.73 percent. The y-axis shows the probability. Image from Wikipedia [17].

When the standard deviation is used to represent uncertainty, there is a 68.3 percent probability that the true value falls within one standard deviation of the measured result [11]:

$$x = \bar{x} \pm \sigma \quad (2.9)$$

Here, x has a 68.3 percent confidence level. This is the standard uncertainty for measurement results [18].

2.3 The uncertainty of the fit parameters using χ^2

Building on the statistical foundations established above, the estimation of fit parameter uncertainties using the χ^2 method is now addressed.

In this paper, a distinction will be made between the individual uncertainty and the join uncertainty. Individual uncertainty refers to the uncertainty associated with a single parameter, considered

independently of the others. It reflects the probability that the true value of this parameter lies within a specific range, regardless of the values of the other parameters. In contrast, joint uncertainty accounts for the uncertainties of all parameters together, including any correlations between them. It describes the probability that the true values of all parameters simultaneously fall within their respective uncertainty ranges. An analogy for this is rolling two 6-sided dice. The individual probability of a single die landing on 6 is 1 in 6. The joint probability of both dice landing on 6 at the same time is 1 in 36. Naturally, when there is only one parameter, the individual uncertainty is equivalent to the joint uncertainty, as there are no other parameters with which it could be jointly uncertain.

Standard deviations typically quantify individual uncertainties. They indicate how much a parameter is expected to vary around its mean value, without accounting for relationships with other parameters.

In this paper, the joint uncertainty is used, as it provides a more comprehensive representation of the combined uncertainty in all parameters. This approach accounts for potential correlations and interactions between parameters, providing a more complete picture than considering individual uncertainties alone.

2.3.1 Obtaining the one-dimensional fit uncertainty

The normalized residuals are a weighted method to determine how much the fit differs from the measured data:

$$R_i = \frac{y_i - y(x_i)}{\sigma_i} \quad (2.10)$$

where y_i is the measured value of data point i , $y(x_i)$ is the fitted value at x_i and σ_i is the error on data point i [19]. The dimensionless quality χ^2 , is a goodness-of-fit parameter and is defined as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_i \frac{(y_i - y(x_i))^2}{\sigma_i^2} = \sum_i R_i^2 \quad (2.11)$$

It can be minimized by optimizing the fit parameters. The χ^2 is used to obtain the curvature matrix near the minimum:

$$A_{jk} = \frac{1}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \chi^2}{\partial a_j \partial a_k} \right|_{\vec{a}^{(0)}} \quad (2.12)$$

where a_j and a_k correspond to the fit parameters and $\vec{a}^{(0)}$ denote the best fit parameter values. The curvature of the χ^2 provides insight in how sensitive it is to changes in the parameters around the minimum. A steep rise in the χ^2 value with respect to a parameter indicates that the parameter is well constrained, leading to a smaller uncertainty. A shallow rise in the χ^2 value, indicates a poorly constrained parameter, which results in a big uncertainty. This is reflected accordingly in the curvature matrix. The off-diagonal elements of the curvature matrix indicate how strongly the fit parameters are coupled or influence each other. The curvature matrix is inverted to attain the covariance matrix:

$$[C] = [A]^{-1} \quad (2.13)$$

Here, the diagonals of the covariance matrix are the variances of the respective the parameters. A matrix is invertible if and only if it is non-singular, which means it must have full rank [20]. The rank of a matrix is the number of columns (or rows) that are linearly independent — both give the same value. Full rank means that *all* rows and columns are linearly independent. For a square $M \times M$ matrix, this means the rank is equal to M . A matrix is said to be ill-conditioned when it has a large condition number, indicating that it is close to being singular. In such cases, numerical operations like inversion or solving linear systems become highly sensitive to rounding errors or perturbations in the data. The condition number of a positive definite matrix [20]:

$$c = \frac{\lambda_{max}}{\lambda_{min}} \quad (2.14)$$

Where c is the condition number, λ_{max} is the biggest eigenvalue and λ_{min} is the smallest eigenvalue of the matrix. For a good fit, the curvature matrix of the χ^2 at its minimum is positive definite. If it is not, this method of calculating the uncertainty will be inaccurate. The curvature matrix is half of the Hessian matrix \mathcal{H} . If $\mathcal{H}(a)$ is positive definite, then the function it is based on has a minimum at a [21]. The only other way it could have a minimum at a is if it were positive semi-definite. However, then one of the eigenvalues would have to be zero and it would not be full rank. This extends to the curvature matrix.

In case of the χ^2 function, an ill-conditioned curvature matrix may be related to strong correlation between parameters. The correlation matrix can be calculated using the covariance matrix:

$$\text{Corr}_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}}{\sqrt{C_{ii} \cdot C_{jj}}} \quad (2.15)$$

A strong correlation between parameters does not automatically indicate an ill-conditioned curvature matrix. However, (near) parameter degeneracy at the coordinates³ of the curvature matrix does cause it to be ill-conditioned and is reflected in strongly correlated parameters. Parameter degeneracy means that two (or more) parameters affect the outcome of the model in a (near) identical manner.

The one-dimensional uncertainty of parameter j :

$$\alpha_{\nu=1,j} = \sqrt{C_{jj}} \quad (2.16)$$

The one-parameter fit uncertainty as shown in Equation 2.16, constitutes the *individual uncertainty*.

2.3.2 Confidence levels for multidimensional fits

While the one-dimensional case provides initial insights into parameter uncertainty, practical applications typically involve multiple parameters. The concept is therefore extended to joint uncertainties in multi-parameter fits.

³In this case near the χ^2 minimum.

Figure 2.5 The error surface for the function $f(x, a, b) = a \cdot x + b$. Here $\Delta\chi^2 = \chi^2 - \chi_{min}^2$, form contours for constant values.⁴

Figure 2.5 shows an example of an error surface. The red dot indicates the values of the parameters for which χ^2 is at its minimum. These are the optimal parameter values. The contours around it correspond to levels of $\Delta\chi^2$ and indicate different levels of uncertainty. The bigger the contour, the more certain that the true values of the parameters fall within it.

⁴All example error surface figures were generated using custom code, see Appendix D.

Figure 2.6 The error surface for the function $f(x, a, b) = a \cdot x + b$. Here $\Delta\chi^2 = \chi^2 - \chi_{min}^2$, form contours for constant values. The dashed blue and green lines signify the value of $a \pm$ the error on a and value of $b \pm$ the error on b respectively. The errors here are the individual errors for each parameter for a single parameter fit. The dashed lines touch the edges of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 1$ contour.

Figure 2.6 shows the $\Delta\chi^2 = 1$ contour, with dashed lines that touch its edges. These lines represent the individual uncertainty ranges for the parameters a (blue) and b (green), as determined using Equation 2.16.

The $\Delta\chi^2 = 1$ contour corresponds to the 68.3% confidence interval for a single parameter, assuming that the model is correct and the measurement errors are normally distributed. This is sometimes referred to as the 1-parameter fit uncertainty, where each parameter is varied independently while all others are held fixed.

In contrast, when estimating uncertainties jointly across multiple parameters, the confidence region is defined by a larger $\Delta\chi^2$ value that depends on the total number of parameters being estimated. For example, the joint 68.3% confidence region for two parameters is defined by a $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$. The appropriate values for up to six parameters are listed in Table 2.1.

ν	1	2	3	4	5	6
$\Delta\chi_\nu^2$	1.00	2.30	3.53	4.72	5.89	7.04

Table 2.1 The value for $\Delta\chi^2$ corresponding to a 68.3 percent confidence level with ν the number of fit parameters [22].

The equation for the *joint uncertainty* of a ν -parameter fit [22]:

$$\alpha_{\nu,j} = \sqrt{C_{jj}} \cdot \sqrt{\Delta\chi_\nu^2} \tag{2.17}$$

where C_{jj} denotes the j th diagonal element of the covariance matrix. For a two-parameter fit, the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour corresponds to a 68.3% confidence region for the true values of the

parameters. This contour, as well as the adjusted errors of the parameters, can be found in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7 The error surface for the function $f(x, a, b) = a \cdot x + b$. Here $\Delta\chi^2 = \chi^2 - \chi_{min}^2$, form contours for constant values. The dashed blue and green lines signify the value of $a \pm$ the error on a and value of $b \pm$ the error on b respectively. The errors here are the correlated errors for each parameter for a two-parameter fit. The $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour corresponds to a 68.3 percent confidence level. The dashed lines touch the edges of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour.

As is customary, the calculated uncertainties are rounded to one significant figure [11]. This convention implies that the relative uncertainty on the reported error values typically falls between 10% and 100%. In this paper, uncertainties are considered acceptably reported if the rounding results in a relative error of less than 10%.

2.3.3 Breakdown of the Quadratic Approximation

In Section 2.3.1, the curvature matrix is introduced and defined by Equation 2.12 as the matrix of second order partial derivatives of the χ^2 function with respect to the fit parameters:

$$A_{jk} = \frac{1}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \chi^2}{\partial a_j \partial a_k} \right|_{\vec{a}^{(0)}} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \chi_0^2}{\partial a_j \partial a_k} \quad (2.18)$$

This expression arises from a Taylor expansion of χ^2 around its minimum, under the assumption that the function is approximately quadratic in the parameters in the vicinity of the best-fit point $\vec{a}^{(0)}$ [23]:

$$\chi^2 \approx \chi_0^2 + \sum_{j=1}^m \left\{ \frac{\delta \chi_0^2}{\delta a_j} (a_j - a_j^{(0)}) \right\} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m \left\{ \frac{\delta^2 \chi_0^2}{\delta a_k \delta a_j} (a_k - a_k^{(0)}) (a_j - a_j^{(0)}) \right\} \quad (2.19)$$

Where a_j and a_k represent the fit parameters, $a_j^{(0)}$ and $a_k^{(0)}$ represent the parameter values near

the best-fit point and χ_0^2 represents the chi squared near the best-fit point. When this approximation holds, the inverse of the curvature matrix provides an estimate of the covariance matrix, and the diagonal elements yield the variances (squared uncertainties) of the fit parameters as described in Section 2.3.1 [23].

However, this quadratic approximation does not always hold. In case where the parameters are significantly nonlinearly correlated, the χ^2 surface may become distorted, i.e. deviate from the expected elliptical geometry. In such cases, higher-order terms in the Taylor expansion of χ^2 become non-negligible near the minimum and the χ_0^2 can no longer be accurately approximated as quadratic. As a result, the curvature matrix no longer accurately reflects the local geometry of the χ^2 surface, and uncertainties derived from its inverse may be underestimated, overestimated, or fail to reflect asymmetries or degeneracies in parameter space. In short, significant nonlinear parameter correlation can cause non-quadratic behavior in the chi squared, which negatively affects the reliability of the uncertainty estimates.

Chapter 3

Approach

The theoretical basis for uncertainty estimation provides the groundwork for practical application. This chapter outlines how the χ^2 -based method was implemented in the NMR analysis software ssNake.

The parameter uncertainty estimation implementation closely follows the theoretical method as outlined in Section 2.3. The following procedure outlines the core steps:

1. **Noise selection:** The user selects a section of the spectrum that contains only noise. Based on this selection, the error bars of the data points are estimated as the standard deviation of the section of noise.
2. **Peak selection:** The user then selects the region containing the peak of interest. To reduce runtime, the χ^2 is only calculated over this selected region.
3. **χ^2 construction:** The fit function, the selected data points, and their corresponding error bars are used to form the χ^2 function.
4. **Second order derivatives:** The second order partial derivatives of χ^2 with respect to the fit parameters are computed. For simplicity, the code differentiates each term in the χ^2 sum individually and then sums the results ¹.
5. **Curvature matrix:** The resulting second order derivatives of χ^2 are divided by two to form the curvature matrix.
6. **Covariance matrix:** The curvature matrix is then inverted to obtain the covariance matrix.
7. **Uncertainty estimation:** The square roots of the diagonal elements of the covariance matrix are computed. These values are scaled based on the number of fit parameters to reflect the joint uncertainties of the parameters.

The following sections elaborate on specific elements of this approach that are important for understanding its implementation.

¹This is valid due to the linearity of differentiation [21]

3.1 Errors on the data points

The uncertainties on the data points, σ_i , are assumed to be uniform and are estimated from the standard deviation of a flat region of the spectrum that contains only noise and no signal. This is justified under the assumption that the noise is Gaussian and homoscedastic.

Figure 3.1 Spectrum with selected noise region and corresponding noise distribution. The left plot displays the full frequency spectrum, with the orange-highlighted region indicating a segment dominated by noise. The right plot shows a histogram of the amplitude values within this noisy segment, overlaid with a normal distribution curve. The distribution’s standard deviation (σ) is annotated. The corresponding error is calculated with Equation 2.5. The histogram of the noise is approximately normally distributed. For more information about the code and data used to generate this figure, see Appendix D.

Figure 3.1, shows that the noise of selected region of the spectrum is roughly normally distributed. The precision of the estimated standard deviation increases with the number of data points in the noise region, as the standard error is inversely proportional to sample size, as described in Equation 2.5. It is important that the selected noise region contains a sufficient number of data points, as the uncertainty in the estimated fit parameter errors depends on the precision of the noise estimate². The relative error from the noisy region of Figure 3.1, which contains a thousand data points, is roughly 2%.

3.2 Second order finite difference approximation

In order to calculate the second order partial derivatives needed for the curvature matrix as shown in Equation 2.12, the central finite difference approximation is used [24]:

$$\frac{df(x)}{dx} \approx \frac{f(x+h) - f(x-h)}{2h} \quad (3.1)$$

for some small value of the step size, h . The advantage of using the central difference approximation is that it has an error of the order h^2 , whereas the forward and backward approximations both have an error of the order h [25]. Since h is taken as $h \rightarrow 0$ to minimize this the introduced error, the central difference approximation is generally more precise.

²See Appendix C.

The second order partial derivative using this method is:

$$\frac{\partial^2 f(x, y)}{\partial x \partial y} \approx \frac{f(x + h_1, y + h_2) - f(x + h_1, y - h_2) - f(x - h_1, y + h_2) + f(x - h_1, y - h_2)}{4h_1h_2} \quad (3.2)$$

Here, x and y are analogous to the parameters a_j and a_k and $f(x, y)$ corresponds to χ^2 from Equation 2.12. Additionally, h_1 and h_2 are the step sizes corresponding to x and y respectively.

$$h_1 = h_2 = 10^{-5} \quad (3.3)$$

3.3 Matrix inversion

As noted in Section 2.3.1, matrix inversion requires the matrix to be non-singular, i.e. have full rank. In the code, `numpy.linalg.inv(A)` is used to invert the curvature matrix to obtain the covariance matrix. This function will raise an error if the matrix is detected to be singular [26]. However, if the matrix is merely ill-conditioned, the function might not raise an error.

3.4 Rescaling the parameter values

In addition to accurate matrix inversion, attention must also be given to numerical stability when parameter values span different orders of magnitude. The following section describes how rescaling is used to address this issue.

In NMR, the order of magnitude can vary significantly between parameters. This can cause several issues.

The second order derivatives needed to calculate the curvature matrix are found using numerical differentiation as discussed in Section 3.2. If the parameter values are very large or very small, the step size may not be the right size. If the parameter is very small, the step size may be relatively big and if the parameter value is very big the relatively small step size may lead to numerical precision issues, even defaulting to zero. This can be solved either using relative step sizes or rescaling the parameters.

The covariance matrix is obtained by taking the inverse of the curvature matrix as seen in Equation 2.13. In Section 2.3.1, it was explained that taking the inverse of an ill-conditioned matrix can be problematic. The scale of the fit parameters inversely influences the scale of the curvature matrix entries: larger parameter values typically correspond to smaller curvatures, and vice versa. Equation 2.14, shows that the condition number of the curvature matrix can be calculated by dividing the largest eigenvalue by the smallest. If the values of the curvature matrix differ greatly in order of magnitude, this can result in eigenvalues that differ greatly in order of magnitude. If this is the case, the matrix will have a very high condition number and thus be ill-conditioned. Hence, parameters that vary strongly in scale can result in an ill-conditioned curvature matrix.

To prevent issues with numerical instability and ill-conditioning caused by large differences in parameter scales, the fit parameters are rescaled prior to optimization. This is done by computing the order of magnitude (referred to as the scale) s_p of a parameter p , and defining a dimensionless scaled parameter $p_s = p/s_p$. For example, if $p = 3145$, then $s_p = 10^3$, and $p_s = 3.145$. A scaled fit function $f_{\text{scaled}}(p_s)$ is then constructed such that the original function is evaluated using the unscaled parameters: $f_{\text{scaled}}(p_s) = f(s_p \cdot p_s)$.

This transformation ensures that the step sizes in the numerical calculation of the curvature matrix are well-matched to the scale of each parameter, improving numerical stability. As a result, the curvature matrix becomes better conditioned, avoiding numerical problems during matrix inversion. After computing the covariance matrix in the scaled space, it is rescaled to recover the covariance matrix in the original parameter space (see proof in Appendix A).

With appropriate rescaling applied to ensure numerical stability, the implementation proceeds to construct the confidence region based on these scaled parameter values.

Results and Discussion

4.1 The implementation in ssNake

Figure 4.1, shows the uncertainty implementation in the Graphic User Interface (GUI) of ssNake. Currently, it is only implemented for the Lorentz/Gaussian fitting option. The spectrum should be fit as normal. The standard deviation of the noise can be calculated by pressing the standard deviation button, which causes the 'Standard Deviation Noise' window to pop up. This is shown in Figure 4.1a. In this window, indices that correspond to a region of the spectrum that contains just noise, no signal, can be entered. After pressing the calculate button, the standard deviation of the noise will be shown next to the corresponding button.

The desired fit for which to calculate the uncertainties can be selected in the combo box. Subsequently, the 'Uncertainty' button can be pressed, which causes the 'Uncertainty' window to appear. This is shown in Figure 4.1b. If the fit was unsuccessful, the user will receive a warning. Moreover, if the standard deviation has not yet been calculated the user will receive a warning. Lastly, if there are active fit parameter selected that are so nonlinearly correlated that they cause the estimated uncertainties to become unreliable (e.g. *Multiplier* and *Integral*) the user will be issued a warning. This will be elaborated on in Section 4.3.2.

In the uncertainty window, the labels and values of the active fit parameters are shown. Note, that only the uncertainties of the active fit parameters will be calculated. In the example shown in Figure 4.1, the *Position*, *Integral*, and *Lorentz* parameters are active fit parameters. The parameter referred to as the *Lorentz* here denotes the Lorentzian linewidth. In contrast, the *Offset*, *Multiplier*, and *Gauss* parameters were locked during the fit. In ssNake's GUI, parameters can be locked or unlocked by selecting the check boxes next to them. A blue check mark indicates that the parameter is locked. Locked parameters are treated as constants during the fitting process, meaning they will not be adjusted. As a result, the program does not calculate uncertainties for these parameters.

In the uncertainty window, the user can enter the region that contains the relevant peak. The χ^2 is calculated for the selected region of the peak, as opposed to the entire spectrum, to reduce runtime. Then, the 'calculate' button can be pressed and the estimated uncertainties will appear

below 'Error:', next to their corresponding parameters.

(a) Pressing the standard deviation button, labeled 'stdev', causes the standard deviation window labeled 'Standard Deviation Noise' to pop up. The user enters the start and end indices of the region containing only noise. After pressing calculate, the standard deviation of the noise will be shown in the text box next to the standard deviation button.

(b) After the standard deviation of the noise has been calculated, the user can select for which fit they want the uncertainties to be calculated using the combo box. In the example, there is only one fit and therefore only one option for the combo box. Pressing the 'Uncertainty' button, causes the 'Uncertainty' window to pop up. The user enters the start and end indices of the region of the relevant peak and presses the calculate button. The calculated uncertainties will then be shown in the boxes below 'Error:', next to their corresponding parameters.

Figure 4.1 The figures show the uncertainty implementation in the GUI of ssNake. This implementation is for the Lorentz/Gauss fitting option. First, the user fits the spectrum as normal. Then, the standard deviation of the noise is calculated as shown in Figure 4.1a. Subsequently, the uncertainties are estimates as outlined in Figure 4.1b. It should be noted that only the uncertainties of active fit parameters, in this example the *Position*, *Integral* and *Lorentz*, are calculated. The parameter referred to as the *Lorentz* here denotes the Lorentzian linewidth.

4.2 Comparisons

After integrating the uncertainty estimation functionality into the ssNake interface, its validity must be evaluated. This section compares the results obtained using the implemented method against alternative approaches to assess its accuracy and reliability.

To verify the reliability of the implementation of the χ^2 uncertainty estimation method, the results are compared to uncertainties obtained using alternative approaches. Ideally, one would compare the calculated uncertainties with those reported in existing NMR spectroscopy literature that uses the Lorentzian/Gaussian fit function. However, a search did not yield any suitable published values. This highlights a general lack of proper uncertainty analysis in the NMR field and illustrates the need for a more accessible approach to estimating fit parameter uncertainties.

4.2.1 Multiple measurements of the same sample

A different method to estimate the uncertainty on the fit parameters, is to infer it from multiple measurements.

Ten spectra of the same sample have been fit for the *Position*, *Integral* and *Lorentz* (Lorentzian linewidth) with the Lorentzian fit function in ssNake ¹. The standard deviations of the fit values denote the individual errors of the parameters. The uncertainties on the fit values for these ten fits were obtained from the χ^2 implementation in ssNake as well. The uncertainties from ssNake represent the joint errors. For a more accurate comparison, the joint errors were scaled to represent the individual errors, to be in accordance with the standard deviations.

¹For details about the data, see Appendix D.

Spectrum #	Relative Position error	Relative Integral error	Relative Lorentz error
0	0.004%	0.6%	0.8%
1	0.004%	0.6%	0.9%
2	0.005%	0.6%	0.9%
3	0.004%	0.6%	0.9%
4	0.004%	0.6%	0.9%
5	0.004%	0.6%	0.9%
6	0.004%	0.6%	0.9%
7	0.004%	0.6%	0.9%
8	0.004%	0.6%	0.9%
9	0.005%	0.6%	0.9%
Standard deviation	0.005% ± 0.001	0.9% ± 0.2	1.1% ± 0.3

Table 4.1 Ten different spectra of the same sample have been fitted for the *Position*, *Integral* and *Lorentz*. The individual errors have been calculated using ssNake. The standard deviations a obtained from the fit values of the same ten fits as the errors. They are calculated using Equation 2.4, where the means are those of the respective fit values. The uncertainties on the standard deviations are calculated using Equation 2.5. All uncertainties are shown as the relative error, a percentage of the corresponding fit value.

Table 4.1, shows the individual errors of the fit parameters from ssNake for ten different measurements of the same sample, as well as the corresponding standard deviations with their error margins. All ten of the errors of both the *Position* and *Lorentz* fall within the error margin of their respective standard deviations. However, all the errors of the *Integral* fall just below the error margin of the corresponding standard deviation. Moreover, all the errors from ssNake are lower than their corresponding standard deviations. This could suggest that the uncertainties from ssNake are an underestimation of the actual uncertainties of the fit parameters.

4.2.2 Monte Carlo simulations

A different way to obtain the uncertainties on the fit parameters is via Monte Carlo simulations [22]. The idea is to simulate various spectra based on the original fit and analyze the spread of the outcomes. The spectra are simulated by taking the best fit of the spectrum and adding random, normally distributed noise to it. The standard deviation of the simulated Gaussian noise is taken as the approximated standard deviation of the noise used to estimate the errors on the data points. Each simulated spectrum is refitted, and the resulting fit parameters are used to compute the mean values and standard deviations, providing estimates of the parameter uncertainties. Given that the simulated spectra use uniform errors based on the same error estimates as those used for the ssNake uncertainties, any mischaracterization of those errors will be carried over to the simulated

spectra. Similarly, if the obtained fit is suboptimal, this mismatch will likewise be propagated to the simulated spectra. This will enable verification of whether the underestimation of the uncertainties, as described in the previous section, arise from inaccuracies or assumptions in the theoretical model or are caused by another source. ²

	Relative Position error	Relative Integral error	Relative Lorentz error
from ssNake	0.0043%	0.60%	0.85%
from simulations	$0.0044\% \pm 0.0001$	$0.59\% \pm 0.01$	$0.86\% \pm 0.02$

Table 4.2 The spectrum has been fit for the *Position*, *Integral* and *Lorentz* in ssNake and a thousand spectra have been simulated with random Gaussian noise based on this fit. The relative individual errors from ssNake are shown as well as the relative individual error from the Monte Carlo simulations. The errors from the simulations are the standard deviations from the simulated fit values. The uncertainty on this standard deviation calculated using Equation 2.5.

Table 4.2 shows the relative individual errors calculated with ssNake alongside those obtained from Monte Carlo simulations. The ssNake errors fall within the simulation error margins. Moreover, the simulated uncertainties closely match the standard deviations for both the *Position* and *Lorentz* parameters in Table 4.1. However, this is not the case for the *Integral*, where the relative error from repeated measurements ($0.9\% \pm 0.2$) is slightly larger than that from the simulations ($0.59\% \pm 0.01$).

This discrepancy suggests that the underestimation of the uncertainty in the *Integral* is due to a mischaracterization of the theoretical model. One possible explanation could be that the simulation's noise estimate does not completely cover the experimental error. As discussed in Section 3.1, the noise was assumed to be uniform and Gaussian. The standard deviation of the noise contributes an estimated error margin of approximately 2% of the relative uncertainty from ssNake (i.e. $0.60\% \pm 0.01$), which cannot fully account for the difference between the standard deviation of the *Integral* across spectra and the uncertainty estimates obtained from simulations and from ssNake, which are in good agreement. Additionally, in that same section, the noise was found to be consistent with a Gaussian distribution. While the assumption of uniform (homoscedastic) noise was not explicitly tested, the assumption of white complex Gaussian noise is common in NMR spectroscopy [5]. There are, however, scenarios where the experimental error can be heteroscedastic [27]. If the experimental error were positively correlated with signal strength, the current method would underestimate the error bars. This is because the error bars are assumed to be uniform and are based on a baseline region with no signal. As a result, the calculated uncertainties would also be proportionally underestimated.

Another possible explanation could be that the fit is suboptimal. This would entail that either the found fit parameters differ from the true χ^2 minimum values or the used theoretical fit model does not fully describe the data. These differences would have to be subtle, as they are not visually discernible. Given that the method used to calculate the uncertainties assumes that the fit is optimal, any deviation may result in less accurate estimates.

²For details about the data and the code used for the simulations, see Appendix D.

While the difference is relatively small in this case, it could be more significant for certain different datasets. Further investigation may be warranted.

4.3 $\Delta\chi^2$ contours

The χ^2 method of calculating uncertainties assumes quadratic behavior of the χ^2 near the minimum. For a two-dimensional χ^2 error surface this means that the contours should be elliptical. Non-quadratic behavior near the minimum, affects the reliability of the calculated uncertainties. However, less than optimal contours does not immediately render the chi squared errors unusable. Nevertheless, for any significant deviations from the expected elliptical geometry, their effect on the reliability of the errors should be considered.

The χ^2 contours of two-parameter fit will be analyzed in this section. These are two-dimensional, which makes it easier to visualize the contour shapes. In Section 2.3.2, it was established that, for a two-parameter fit, the uncertainties on the fit parameters reflect a 68.3% confidence interval if the error boundaries touch the edges of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour. The calculated errors on the fit parameters have one significant figure. As mentioned previously, this implies a fractional uncertainty on the errors between 10 and 100 percent [11]. Therefore, a difference between the contour and the calculated uncertainties of less than 10% is considered acceptable, barring other major sources of error. For details about the figures, see Appendix D.

4.3.1 Quadratic behavior

Figure 4.2 The $\Delta\chi^2$ contour plot of the parameters *Position* and *Integral*. The errors on the parameters are denoted by $\chi_{min}^2 \pm \alpha_{Position}$, the blue dashed lines, and $\chi_{min}^2 \pm \alpha_{Integral}$, the green dashed lines, respectively. A two percent range on these errors is shown in the same colors.

Figure 4.2, shows the $\Delta\chi^2$ contours of the fit of the *Position* and *Integral*. The contours around the χ^2 minimum form the expected elliptical shapes. The calculated errors are within a 2% range of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour. These uncertainties on the parameters are reliable and correspond to the 68.3% confidence level.

Figure 4.3 The $\Delta\chi^2$ contour plot of the parameters *Integral* and *Lorentz*. The errors on the parameters are denoted by $\chi_{min}^2 \pm \alpha_{Integral}$, the blue dashed lines, and $\chi_{min}^2 \pm \alpha_{Lorentz}$, the green dashed lines, respectively. A two percent range on these errors is shown in the same colors.

Figure 4.3, shows the $\Delta\chi^2$ contours of the fit of the *Integral* and *Lorentz*. The contours around the χ^2 minimum form the expected elliptical shapes. The calculated errors are within a 2% range of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour. These uncertainties on the parameters accurately convey 68.3% confidence level of their fit parameters as well.

Most combinations of fit parameters yield results consistent with expectations. However, certain parameter combinations may deviate from the anticipated elliptical geometry, potentially rendering the associated error estimates unreliable. This behavior is discussed in more detail in Section 4.3.2.

4.3.2 Non-quadratic behavior

Non-quadratic behavior in well-behaved fits can be caused by nonlinear fit parameter interactions. When parameters are nonlinearly compensating for each other near the chi squared minimum, this results in deformed contours. Small deviations from the expected geometry will not significantly affect the reliability of the calculated uncertainties. However, when the non-quadratic behavior is significant, this will result in a significant mismatch between the calculated uncertainties and the 68.3% confidence contour. Strong correlation between fit parameters may indicate significant deformed χ^2 contours. However, it does not guarantee it. In this section, the 2-dimensional error surfaces of strongly correlated parameters are investigated. A difference of less than 10% between the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ is considered acceptable, barring other major error sources.

	Offset	Multiplier	Position	Integral	Lorentz	Gauss
Offset	1.0000	-0.0125	-0.0059	-0.0139	-0.7119	0.5825
Multiplier	-0.0125	1.0000	0.0001	-0.9995	0.0137	-0.0115
Position	-0.0059	0.0001	1.0000	0.0001	0.0018	0.0057
Integral	-0.0139	-0.9995	0.0001	1.0000	0.0150	-0.0126
Lorentz	-0.7119	0.0137	0.0018	0.0150	1.0000	-0.9294
Gauss	0.5825	-0.0115	0.0057	-0.0126	-0.9294	1.0000

Table 4.3 Correlation matrix of the fitted parameters near the χ^2 minimum: Offset, Multiplier, Position, Integral, Lorentz, and Gauss. Values close to ± 1 indicate strong linear relationships between parameters.

Table 4.3, shows the correlation between each of the fit parameters, found using Equation 2.15. When the correlation of two parameters is close to ± 1 , the parameters are highly correlated and this indicates a strong linear relationship. The correlations of a parameter with itself is naturally equal to one.

The correlation coefficient between *Multiplier* and *Integral* is -0.9995 , which suggests an extremely strong negative linear relationship.

Figure 4.4 The $\Delta\chi^2$ contour plot for the parameters *Multiplier* and *Integral*, which exhibit a very strong negative correlation ($\text{Corr} = -0.9995$) near the χ^2 minimum. The elongated, curved shape of the error surface reflects the strong nonlinear parameter dependency and near-singularity of the curvature matrix in this region of parameter space.

Figure 4.4, shows the $\Delta\chi^2$ contour plot for the *Multiplier* and *Integral*. Here, only one fit was done, which results in the *Multiplier* and *Integral* having an very similar effect on the fit. They are nonlinearly compensating for each other, causing the contours to be deformed. The contour plot deviates significantly from the expected elliptical shapes indicating that the calculated uncertainties are rendered completely unreliable.

The correlation between the *Lorentz* and *Gauss* is $\text{Corr} = -0.9294$ according to the Table 4.3, this also suggests a strong negative linear relationship, albeit a little less strong than that of *Multiplier* and *Integral*.

Figure 4.5 The $\Delta\chi^2$ contour plot for the parameters *Lorentz* and *Gauss*, which exhibit a very strong negative correlation ($\text{Corr} = -0.9294$) near the χ^2 minimum. The contour lines deviate from the expected elliptical geometry, forming warped shapes characteristic of nonlinearly correlated parameters. The calculated errors on the *Lorentz* are within a 2% range and the calculated errors on the *Gauss* are within a 16% range of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour.

Figure 4.5, shows the $\Delta\chi^2$ contour plot for the *Lorentz* and *Gauss*. The contour lines deviate from the expected elliptical geometry, forming warped shapes characteristic of nonlinearly correlated parameters. This suggests that the parameters are not independently constrained by the data near the minimum. The error on the *Lorentz* fall within a 2% range of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour. In the figure, the green dashed lines that indicate the $\chi_{min} \pm$ the error on the *Gauss*, both over- and underestimate the 68.3 percent confidence region denoted by the dashed magenta contour. Both of the errors on the *Gauss* fall within a 16% range of $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour. This 16% difference is bigger than than the acceptable 10% error. However, compared to the 10%-100% fractional uncertainty range corresponding to one significant figure, it is on the lower end.

Figure 4.6 The $\Delta\chi^2$ contour plot for the parameters *Lorentz* and *Gauss*. A thousand spectra have been simulated by adding random Gaussian noise to the fit. These spectra have in turn been fitted for the *Lorentz* and *Gauss* and their fit values are shown as points in the figure. The blue circles indicate the simulated values that fall outside of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour, the green triangles the values that fall inside the contour and inside of the calculated error margins and the orange squares the values that fall inside the contour but outside the calculated error margins.

Figure 4.6, shows simulated parameter values plotted on top of the *Lorentz-Gauss* chi squared contours. The values have been using the same method that was used in Section 4.2.2: The fit was used to simulate 1000 spectra by adding random Gaussian noise based on the standard deviation of the noise of the original spectrum. In total, 69.1% of the simulated points fall within the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour. This roughly agrees with the expected 68.3%. The orange squares in Figure 4.6 correspond to parameter values that lie within the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour but outside the calculated uncertainties on the parameters. Overall, this discrepancy affects only 0.7% of the total points, indicating a relatively minor difference. Moreover, 82.7% of the points fall within the error margins of both the *Lorentz* and *Gauss*. Since the χ^2 contour is elliptical and the uncertainties are defined by constant parameter values (rectangular bounds), the uncertainty margins correspond to a somewhat higher confidence level than the actual elliptical contour. This overstates the actual 68.3% confidence interval because the rectangle always contains more area than the ellipse. However, while the lower uncertainty bound on the *Gauss* is underestimated, the overall uncertainty margins still provide a conservative representation of the true confidence.

While it cannot be assumed that the rounding fully absorbs the error introduced by the deformed *Lorentz-Gauss* contour, the effect remains relatively minor and does not substantially impact the reliability of the results. However, the effect of the nonlinear correlation of the *Lorentz* and *Gauss* on the chi squared behavior near the minimum as well as the effect on the reliability of the uncertainties should be further researched.

The correlation between the *Lorentz* and *Offset* is $\text{Corr} = -0.7119$. While it is significantly lower than the correlation of the *Lorentz* and *Gauss* and the correlation of the *Multiplier* and *Integral*, it is still strong enough that its effect on the χ^2 contours should be investigated further.

Figure 4.7 The $\Delta\chi^2$ contour plot for the parameters *Lorentz* and *Offset*, which exhibit a strong negative correlation ($\text{Corr} = -0.7119$) near the χ^2 minimum. The contour lines form the expected elliptical geometry. The calculated errors are within a 2% range of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour.

The contour plot of the *Offset* and *Lorentz* can be seen in Figure 4.7. The contour lines form the expected elliptical geometry. This suggests that the parameters are linearly constrained by the data near the minimum for the calculated errors to be reliable. However, given the strong correlation, the behavior of the χ^2 function near the minimum should be investigated further for different fit data.

The *Offset* and *Gauss* have a moderately strong positive correlation of $\text{Corr} = 0.5825$.

Figure 4.8 The $\Delta\chi^2$ contour plot for the parameters *Gauss* and *Offset*, which exhibit a moderately strong positive correlation ($\text{Corr} = 0.5825$) near the χ^2 minimum. The contour lines resemble the expected elliptical geometry, however, they are slightly warped. The calculated error on the *Offset* lies within 1% of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour. The calculated error on the *Gauss* lies within 7% of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour.

Figure 4.8, shows the χ^2 contours of the *Offset* and *Gauss* near the χ^2 minimum. The contours are near elliptical, but they are a little warped. This leads to calculated errors that deviate more from the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour. The calculated errors on the *Offset* lie within 1% of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour. The calculated errors on the *Gauss* lie within 7% of the $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30$ contour. Therefore, since this difference of 7% is less than the acceptable 10%, the uncertainties remain well within the acceptable range. However, with different fit data, the contours could become more distorted, potentially making the uncertainties less reliable. Further investigation is required.

All other correlations shown in Table 4.3 are weak or negligible. Therefore, it is unlikely that the the reliability of the calculated uncertainties are adversely affected by non-quadratic behavior of the χ^2 contours.

4.4 Unoptimized step size for numerical differentiation

In order to calculate the error of the fit parameters, the second order derivative of the χ^2 is needed, as seen in Equation 2.12. In the code, this is done using the second order central finite difference approximation as seen in Equation 3.2. Here h_1 and h_2 are the respective step sizes of the parameters x and y . The step size that is used in the code can be found in Equation 3.3. A way to get a more precise estimation of the needed second order derivative is by using a more optimized step size. A method to estimate a optimal step size is:

$$h_{opt} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_A}{|\Phi|}} \quad (4.1)$$

where ϵ_A is the bound on absolute error in computed function values and Φ is the finite difference approximation to the second derivative [28]. Since h_{opt} is needed to calculate the finite difference approximation, a different estimation is used for this.

$$\hat{c}(\Phi) = \frac{4\epsilon_A}{h_s^2} |\Phi| \quad (4.2)$$

Here $\hat{c}(\Phi)$ is the condition error in approximating the second derivative by finite difference method and h_s is the trial step size:

$$h_s = 2(1 + |x|) \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_A}{1 + |f|}} \quad (4.3)$$

where $|x|$ is of the order unity and f is the exact value of the function. The step size h_s from Equation 4.3 is used as an initial assumption. Using trial and error it is increased or decreased until $\hat{c}(\Phi)$ lies between 0.001 and 0.1. After an acceptable value for h_s is reached, it is used to calculate the approximation for Φ , which is in turn used to find the optimal step size h_{opt} .

However, when calculating the second order derivative for the curvature matrix as seen in Equation 2.12, it is taken as a sum over all data points. And this for all possible combinations of parameters for which the error is being calculated. Using the method outlined above, for all points and all combinations of parameters would be too expensive on the runtime of the program. Preferably, a method is found that compromises between a more optimized step size and not being too inefficient. Alternatively, the error that is introduced using the suboptimal step size can be calculated and reflected in the rounding of the final uncertainty. However, if the error due to the derivative is bigger than the calculated uncertainty, this may prove difficult.

4.5 Ill-conditioned matrix

In Section 2.3.1, it is explained that when a matrix is ill-conditioned, that it is close to being singular. In such cases, numerical operations like matrix inversion become extremely susceptible to rounding errors or small changes in the data. In the chi squared method of calculating the uncertainties, the curvature matrix is inverted to obtain the covariance matrix. The function that is used in the code to invert the matrix, as outlined in Section sec: Matrix inversion, may not raise an error if the matrix is ill-conditioned. Therefore, if the curvature matrix is ill-conditioned, this may affect the reliability of the calculated errors.

The condition number of the matrix is a quantitative measure of how ill-conditioned the matrix is. It can be easily determined using the function: `numpy.linalg.cond` [29]. However, establishing the acceptable range for the condition number for the use of calculating reliable uncertainty estimates using the χ^2 method requires further research. A small degree of ill-conditioning is acceptable, as long as it does not compromise the reliability. The effect of the condition number on the accuracy of the calculated errors should be investigated and an acceptable range for the condition number

should be established.

Nevertheless, based on the comparisons done in Section 4.2, the curvature matrix seems to be well-conditioned enough for it to not significantly affect the accuracy of the calculated uncertainties.

4.6 Future work

Chapter 4 outlined two shortcomings of the current method: the uncertainties appear to be slightly underestimated, and certain combinations of fit parameters result in non-quadratic behavior of the χ^2 contours.

The former is likely due to a subtle mischaracterization of the theoretical model. Possible contributing factors include incomplete characterization of the experimental error, a suboptimal fit model or fit parameters that do not reflect the true χ^2 minimum. Both the behavior of the noise and the quality of the model can be assessed by examining the fit residuals. An increased spread of residuals near the peak regions may indicate correlated experimental error, whereas systematic patterns in the residuals suggest model inadequacy. Additionally, the proximity of the fit to the true χ^2 minimum should be evaluated to rule out optimization related deviations.

Solving the latter issue is less straight forward. For the *Multiplier-Integral* parameter combination, the behavior of the χ^2 contours may behave more quadratic if more than one fit is done at the same time. In that case, the *Multiplier* will affect the behavior of all the fits, whereas the *Integral* will only affect their corresponding fit. In the case that there is only one fit, it may be generally better to not use the *Multiplier* as a fit parameter, because it will act almost identically to the *Integral*.

A possible solution for the *Lorentz* and *Gauss* having very similar effects on the fit near the minimum may be to combine both into a single fit parameter. This combined parameter would determine the degree of Lorentzian character relative to the degree of Gaussian character of the fit.

Alternatively, a different method of determining the uncertainty of the fit parameters could be used if the chi squared method falls short. For instance, using Monte Carlo simulations like what was done in Section 4.2.2.

Moreover, the chi squared behavior near the minimum has only been analyzed for one spectrum. To be rigorous, it should be further investigated for different data sets. This should be done to ensure that possible nonlinear parameter couplings fall within the acceptable error margin for all well-behaved fits.

Furthermore, there are some less critical concerns with the method outlined in Chapter 4. Namely, the unoptimized step size that is used for the numerical differentiation and the possibility of the curvature matrix being ill-conditioned. In Section 4.4, a way to calculate a more optimized step size is described. However, this method would likely be computationally heavy. Further research into the a balanced method of obtaining a more optimal step size for numerical differentiation may be beneficial for limiting the error that is introduced. Section 4.5, expands on the condition number. This is an easily determinable quantitative measure of a matrix's ill-conditioning. However, an acceptable range for this value needs to be established before this can be implemented. Overall, it may be beneficial to do a more thorough error analysis of the method used to calculate the

uncertainty, to identify the biggest sources of error. This would provide a clearer picture of the reliability of the uncertainties of the parameters. On top of that, it may provide insight into which parts can and should be further optimized.

Besides the shortcomings of the current program, there are several features that should be implemented before it has practical use in NMR data analysis.

Currently, ssNake shows a set number of significant figures for each parameter. To be able to better utilize the uncertainties it would be better to round the parameter values based on the calculated uncertainties. Otherwise, if the value is rounded to a bigger digit than the uncertainties, the accurate confidence in the value could still not be properly reported.

NMR spectra generally have overlapping peaks. In ssNake, each peak has a separate function. If there are overlapping peaks, their functions are combined into a super-function. When a fit is done, this super-function is optimized to achieve the best fit. Currently, the uncertainties of each fit function is calculated independently from the other functions. For overlapping peaks, the uncertainties should be calculated using the super-function. Given that ssNake already forms this super-function for overlapping peaks, implementing uncertainty functionality for this would be fairly straightforward. It would mainly consist of passing the right information to the uncertainty program as well as adapting the graphic user interface for this. However, this may cause new nonlinear fit parameters couplings to arise. If multi-peak fit functionality is implemented, the behavior of the chi squared should be rigorously investigated.

In ssNake, there are several different fitting options. The method outlined in this paper and implemented in ssNake only provides an option for the Lorentzian/Gaussian fit. For the future, it may be beneficial to provide uncertainty calculator tools for the other fit options as well. Given that the chi squared method generally works for any fit function, as long as the noise is Gaussian and the fit parameters are linearly correlated, it may be possible to expand the current program to work for the other fit options as well.

The current implementation of the program uses the chi-squared method to estimate the uncertainties of the fit parameters, which is valid only under the assumption that the model provides an accurate description of the data. However, this assumption is not explicitly tested within the program. While the program does issue a warning when the minimization of χ^2 has not yet converged, this only indicates that the optimal parameter values have not been reached—it does not guarantee that the final model is an adequate representation of the data.

Without a formal goodness-of-fit test, the program leaves it to the user to visually assess the quality of the fit. This approach is subjective and may lead to situations where a poor fit is inadvertently accepted, leading to unreliable uncertainty estimates for the parameters. A poor fit can occur even if the χ^2 minimization has converged, for example, if the chosen model is fundamentally incorrect or if the model is correct but certain fit parameters are locked.

Moreover, visually identifying a bad fit may be especially difficult or even impossible if the differences between the model and the data are subtle. In some cases, the discrepancies can be so minor that they are hardly noticeable by eye, further increasing the risk of accepting an inadequate model without realizing it.

By incorporating a goodness-of-fit test, such as evaluating the reduced chi-squared statistic or

analyzing the normalized residuals, the program can provide a more objective measure of the fit quality. Such an improved method of checking the goodness of fit would help the user identify situations where the model does not adequately describe the data, ensuring that the uncertainty estimates for the fit parameters are based on a valid model and reliable data. Consequently, the addition of a goodness-of-fit test would strengthen the reliability of the program's results and reduce the risk of drawing incorrect conclusions from poorly fitting models.

Conclusion

In summary, the chi-squared approach to calculating uncertainties on the fit parameters has proven to be a viable approach for NMR spectroscopy fitting and has been successfully integrated into the preexisting NMR analysis software, ssNake. However, certain limitations and areas for improvement have been identified and require further work. For instance, the minor underestimation of the uncertainties, likely due to a mischaracterization of the theoretical model. Additionally, certain fit parameter combinations are nonlinearly correlated, which causes non-quadratic behavior of the χ^2 near its minimum. Consequently, this affects the reliability of the calculated errors. Nevertheless, while the uncertainties of the fit parameters are a slight underestimation, the differences appear to be generally modest. However, the reliability of the calculated errors should be investigated in more detail.

Furthermore, there are several features that need to be implemented before this uncertainty functionality is suited for practical use. In particular, functionality for multi-peak fits, proper parameter value rounding and a goodness-of-fit test.

Overall, while the current implementation offers a promising approach to uncertainty estimation in NMR spectroscopy, addressing these remaining challenges is essential for ensuring its accuracy and reliability in practical applications. With further refinements, this method has the potential to make the calculation of uncertainties in quantitative NMR analyses more accessible and reliable.

Chapter 6

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Appendix A

Covariance Transformation under Parameter Scaling

Let each fit parameter a_j be scaled by a parameter-specific factor s_j , such that the scaled parameter is defined as:

$$a_{s,j} = \frac{a_j}{s_j}$$

or in vector notation: $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{S}\mathbf{a}_s$, where $\mathbf{S} = \text{diag}(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n)$ is a diagonal matrix of scaling factors.

Since the scaled fit function $f_s(\mathbf{a}_s) = f(\mathbf{S}\mathbf{a}_s)$ returns the same values as the original fit function $f(\mathbf{a})$, the value of the χ^2 function (Equation 2.11) remains unchanged under this transformation. However, the derivatives with respect to $a_{s,j}$ and a_j differ by a scaling factor.

Using the multivariate chain rule, the curvature matrix in the scaled parameter space becomes:

$$A_{s,jk} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \chi^2}{\partial a_{s,j} \partial a_{s,k}} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \chi^2}{\partial a_j \partial a_k} \cdot \frac{\partial a_j}{\partial a_{s,j}} \cdot \frac{\partial a_k}{\partial a_{s,k}} = s_j s_k A_{jk}$$

or, rearranged:

$$A_{jk} = \frac{1}{s_j s_k} A_{s,jk}$$

Taking the inverse to compute the covariance matrix (Equation 2.13), the transformation becomes:

$$C_{jk} = (A^{-1})_{jk} = s_j s_k (A_s^{-1})_{jk} = s_j s_k C_{s,jk}$$

Thus, the covariance matrix in the original parameter space can be obtained from the scaled covariance matrix via:

$$\boxed{C = \mathbf{S} C_s \mathbf{S}}$$

or, in component form:

$$C_{jk} = s_j C_{s,jk} s_k$$

This shows that the scaling operation preserves the structure of the uncertainty propagation and allows safe computation in scaled parameter space, with a well-defined rescaling to return to physical units.

Appendix B

Uncertainty on the standard deviation

The standard error on the mean (SDOM) is defined as:

$$\text{SDOM} = \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}$$

where s is the sample standard deviation and n is the number of measurements.

The relative uncertainty on the SDOM is given by [30]:

$$\frac{\delta(\text{SDOM})}{\text{SDOM}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2n-2}}$$

Since SDOM is directly proportional to s (with \sqrt{n} being a constant), their relative uncertainties are the same:

$$\frac{\delta(\text{SDOM})}{\text{SDOM}} = \frac{\delta s}{s}$$

Thus, the relative uncertainty on the standard deviation s is:

$$\frac{\delta s}{s} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2n-2}}$$

and therefore the absolute uncertainty on the standard deviation is:

$$\delta s = \frac{s}{\sqrt{2n-2}}$$

Impact of Noise Standard Deviation Uncertainty on χ^2 -Based Parameter Uncertainties

The uncertainties on the data points, denoted σ_i , are assumed to be uniform and are estimated based on the standard deviation of a flat, signal-free region of the spectrum, as defined in Equation 2.4. The standard error of the sample standard deviation, which quantifies the uncertainty in this estimate, is given by:

$$\delta s = \frac{s}{\sqrt{2n-2}},$$

where s is the sample standard deviation and n is the number of data points in the noise region. This uncertainty propagates into the final uncertainties on the fit parameters.

The chi-squared statistic is defined as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_i \frac{(y_i - y(x_i))^2}{\sigma_i^2}.$$

Assuming uniform uncertainties, i.e., $\sigma_i = \sigma$ for all i , this simplifies to:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \sum_i (y_i - y(x_i))^2.$$

We define the reduced chi-squared quantity as:

$$\chi_{\text{red}}^2 = \sum_i (y_i - y(x_i))^2,$$

which gives:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \chi_{\text{red}}^2.$$

The curvature matrix is defined by:

$$A_{jk} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \chi^2}{\partial a_j \partial a_k} = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \chi_{\text{red}}^2}{\partial a_j \partial a_k}.$$

This motivates the definition of a reduced curvature matrix A_{red} such that:

$$A = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} A_{\text{red}}.$$

The covariance matrix is then given by:

$$C = A^{-1} = \left(\frac{1}{\sigma^2} A_{\text{red}} \right)^{-1} = \sigma^2 A_{\text{red}}^{-1}.$$

Defining the reduced covariance matrix as:

$$C_{\text{red}} = A_{\text{red}}^{-1},$$

we obtain:

$$C = \sigma^2 C_{\text{red}}.$$

The uncertainty on a fit parameter a_j at confidence level ν is then:

$$\alpha_{\nu,j} = \sigma \cdot \sqrt{C_{jj}^{\text{red}}} \cdot \sqrt{\Delta \chi_{\nu}^2}.$$

If the true noise level is instead σ_{true} , the corresponding true parameter uncertainty is:

$$\alpha_{\nu,j}^{\text{true}} = \sigma_{\text{true}} \cdot \sqrt{C_{jj}^{\text{red}}} \cdot \sqrt{\Delta \chi_{\nu}^2}.$$

This gives the relationship:

$$\alpha_{\text{sample}} = \alpha_{\text{true}} \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{sample}}}{\sigma_{\text{true}}} \right),$$

and equivalently:

$$\alpha_{\text{true}} = \alpha_{\text{sample}} \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{true}}}{\sigma_{\text{sample}}} \right).$$

This shows that any error in the estimate of the noise level σ_{sample} directly scales the final uncertainties on the fit parameters. Underestimating the noise leads to underestimated uncertainties, and vice versa.

Since the true noise level can be written as:

$$\sigma_{\text{true}} = \sigma_{\text{sample}} \pm \delta \sigma_{\text{sample}}$$

the propagated uncertainty on the fit parameters becomes:

$$\alpha_{\text{true}} = \alpha_{\text{sample}} \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{sample}} \pm \delta \sigma_{\text{sample}}}{\sigma_{\text{sample}}} \right) = \alpha_{\text{sample}} \cdot \left(1 \pm \frac{\delta \sigma_{\text{sample}}}{\sigma_{\text{sample}}} \right).$$

The term $\frac{\delta\sigma_{\text{sample}}}{\sigma_{\text{sample}}}$ is the *relative uncertainty* in the noise estimate. As previously shown:

$$\delta\sigma_{\text{sample}} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{sample}}}{\sqrt{2n-2}},$$

so the relative uncertainty is:

$$\frac{\delta\sigma_{\text{sample}}}{\sigma_{\text{sample}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2n-2}}.$$

Therefore, the uncertainty in the estimated parameter uncertainty due to noise estimation is:

$$\alpha_{\text{true}} = \alpha_{\text{sample}} \cdot \left(1 \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{2n-2}}\right),$$

and

Relative error in $\alpha_{\text{sample}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2n-2}}$
--

This highlights that the reliability of the estimated parameter uncertainties depends on how well the noise level is estimated, which in turn improves with the number of points n in the selected noise region.

Appendix D

Research data management

To ensure transparency and reproducibility, all data and code used in this thesis have been made publicly available in a dedicated Zenodo repository created and maintained by the author [31].

- **Repository title:** *Data and code for bachelor thesis: "Parameter Uncertainty Estimation in NMR Spectral Fitting Using ssNake"*
- **Author:** Jay Beekwilder
- **DOI:** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15790377>
- **Year of publication:** 2025

The repository contains:

- All data used in this thesis (e.g. NMR spectra, estimated uncertainties, etc.)
- Source code for all analysis and figure generation scripts
- The parameter uncertainty estimation code
- A graphical user interface (GUI) extension developed to integrate with existing open-source software ssNake
- A `README.md` file describing the repository structure, usage instructions, and software dependencies